

SPOKEN LANGUAGE OF KONISPOL

Linguistics

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Anila Shorri

University of Tirana – Albania.

Abstract

The linguistic wealth of the Albanian language is not only an expression of its standard version. Its dialects are also part of its wealth, as it is the case with any other languages. Each dialect includes important and specific lexicological and linguistic elements, which make it important to do some research. The Tosk dialect, as a dialect of the Albanian language, is particularly important. It includes precious elements, such as the spoken çam dialect of the town of Konispol, whose research would enrich the Albanian language. Thus, the characteristics of the spoken language of Konispol in this article are only a part of this wealth. As any other dialects, the Konispol's one includes certain characteristics, such as phraseological units, whose research is of interest for linguistics. The article addresses this dialect from several perspectives, identifying the large linguistic assets it contains. The article addresses the linguistic and lexicological treasure of the spoken language of Konispol, which is a subdialect of çam, both belonging to the Tosk dialect.

The town of Konispol is located in the South of Albania, about forty kilometers southeast of the city of Saranda. The town is built on a plateau 250-300 metres above the sea level, and is bordered by the Mountain of Saraçindi in the north (1036 meters a.s.l.), Cjepuri and suburbs of the village of Vërvë east, Narta hills (700 meters a.s.l.) deprived of high vegetation south, and the Ionian Sea in the West (on the border with Greece).

Well, the city is built on the southern slope of Saraçindi Mountain in the shape of a plane tree on a nice piece of land with a pleasant sea view, as prolongations of some beautiful rough mountain crests.

Life in Konispol dates back to 2600 years ago, as discoveries in Kreshmoi Cave show. Its population today is about 2500, and since century XVII-XVIII, there has been a spread of the Islam culture in this town, especially in the religious sites.

Konispol has a tough terrain. Its inhabitants have had close relationships with those of Filati, Sajadha, Corfu, etc. through marriage, economy, and commerce. They have co-habited, with each preserving their individual tradition. “*Shperjëm mish e mirrjëm rroba*” (We would bring meat there and we would get clothes on our way back”. *Kur jeshëm të vogjël na thoshnej nana: “Po i bëre detirat që do t’japi jot ëmë do sjell koko nga Filati”* (When we were kids, mother told us “If you do what I ask you to do, I will bring you nice things from Filati).

Being that there were no doctors or pharmacies in Konispol, people would go to Corfu to see a doctor, and buy medications there. The same happened with the construction materials, which Konispol inhabitants would bring from Corfu: “*Kur jeshin njëherë për vdekël, agaj vate në Korfuz e më mori ilaxhet. Ishjën të mira ato se këtu s’keshëm gjë*” (When I was close to death once, my husband went to Corfu to get my medications. They were good, and we had none of that here).

In addition to trade, Konispoli inhabitants are also related through marriages with their above-mentioned neighbors. Once borders were established, such relations stopped.

Due to its tough terrain, Konispoli local people live mostly on livestock production, but there is also an increasing number of people living by cultivating olive trees and citrus trees over the last decade.

As my father has told me, and as I have read on the book of the late Skënder Mullai “History of Konispol”, the people of this town have demonstrated at certain times in their history that they never welcomed enemies, they hated injustice, and that they joined the armed war to defend their freedom.

This is confirmed by several famous historical figures like Muharrem Rushiti, Muhamet Kuçuku (the first author known in the entire region), Abdullah Sulejman Konispoli, Osman Taka, Xhafer Goxhai, Muharrem Shorri, Mustafa Ibrahim, Hysejn Shehu, Shaban Kucuku, Musa Beqiri, Haxhi Kasemi, etc.

The Konispol people have always been very keen in education. Thus, the first Albanian language was opened in 1910 with Italian being the mandatory language. In 1925, Konispol had already an elementary school of three teachers: Qamil Izeti (the head teacher), Bido Sejko, and Rexhep Demi.

It was in 1931, when the first school for girls was opened with about 20 of them. The building was owned by the *vakëf*. It was a one-room building built in 1880. Afterwards, there was an increasing interest in education, and this was proven by the additional classrooms and teachers.

As for religion, historical records show that Konispol people belonged to orthodox religion, but they turned into Muslims since 1700, i.e. they embraced the Islam religion.

Local people of Konispol consider themselves *çam*. The elderly from Konispol and the surrounding villages say: *Camëri i thon që c’ban ki lumi i Shalsit reposh e jaram në Tre Gurt e Zes në Prevezë*.

Nowadays, the large economic and cultural development has increasingly enabled an influence of the literary language on the spoken language of Konispol. However, I have tried to collect material from different people in different areas, such as phonetics, morphology, syntax, lexicology, and toponyms.

I am going to try to describe in this article the most general features of the *çam* spoken language, which even though the closest to the Greek territory, manages to fanatically preserve its language, customs and tradition.

KONISPOL SPOKEN LANGUAGE FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE DIFFERENT DIALECTS OF THE ALBANIAN LANGUAGE

From the dialect perspective, the spoken language of the town of the Konispol belongs to the Tosk dialect, because it demonstrates distinguishing features in terms of phonetics, grammar, and lexicology compared to other areas belonging to the Geg dialect.

If we refer to a more detailed division of the Tosk dialect, Konispol's spoken language belongs to the southern Tosk dialect because of the following characteristics:

a) the vocal system does not include the vowel *y*, which is replaced by *i* or *u*, e.g. *di* “*dy*”, *pite* “*pyete*”, *dizet* “*dyzetë*”, *mbilli* “*mbylli*”, *friu* “*fryu*”, *grika* “*gryka*”, *burek* “*byrek*”, *umër* “*Ymër*”, *dufeq* “*dyfek*”, etc.

b) no diphthongs, but only pairs of vowels, such as *ua*, *ie* for example, *duar*, *grua*, *ftua*, *u zgjua*, *bie*, *shpie*, *ziej*, etc.

c) there is a series of long vowel phonemes, and a strong *e* following ending consonants which are pronounced as *ë* in all cases, for example: *fëmër*, *e njëte* “*e enjte*”, *qëndër*, *vënd*, *mënde*, *zëmër*, etc.

If we stick to the dialect division, the spoken language of Konispol would fall into the *çam* dialect, because;

- It still preserves the old pairs of consonants *kl* and *gl*

For example: *klumusht* “*qumësht*”, *klau* “*qau*”, *shkleu* “*shqeu*”, *glisht* “*gisht*”, *nglet* “*ngjet*”, *zglodhi* “*zgjodhi*”, *u zglat* “*u zgjat*”, *glëmi* “*gjëmbi*”

- It has preserves the *-l* consonant, which has become *-j* across the entire Albanian language, example *val* “*vaj*”, *gola* “*goja*”, *bilë* “*bilë*” etc. *Vrava glishtin edhe klava sa u shkleva* “*Vrava gishtin edhe qava sa u shqeva*”.

- The analytical forms of the passive voice are formed by the active voice plus pronounce, for example *u ka zgatur* “*është zgatur*”, *u ka fshehur* “*është fshehur*”, *u ka xhinosur* “*është xhinosur*”, etc.

- It uses *-l* ending, forming action verbs and motion nouns, for example *vatël* “*vajtje*”, *lidhël* “*lidhje*”, *patël* “*pasuri*”, *pjekël* “*pjekje*”, *Bejkushël* “*e shoqja e Bejkushit*”, *nipël* “*nusja e nipit*”, *vdekël* “*vdekje*”, *gonël, gonla* “*vajza e djalit*”

- It still preserves the vowel *-i* for example *ill* “*yll*”, *di* “*dy*”, *dizet* “*dyzetë*”, *pies* “*pyes*”, *frin* “*fryn*”, *mbill* “*mbyll*”, *grika* “*gryka*”, etc.

The spoken language of the town of Konispol fall into the first areal, given its smaller number of vowels. It only has 6 vowels, lacking the phoneme *y*

THE SPOKEN LANGUAGE OF THE TOWN OF KONISPOL. PHONETIC FEATURES OF THE SPOKEN LANGUAGE OF THE TOWN OF KONISPOL

The spoken language of the town of Konispol preserves some phonetic features, which distinguish it from other forms of the Tosk dialect.

- Thus, this dialect still preserves the pairs of consonants *kl*, *gl*, and *lk*, which are now replaced in the literary language by the phonemes *q*, *gj* for example *kluaj* “*quaj*”, *klaj* “*qaj*”, *shkleu* “*shqeu*”, *kliç* “*kyç*”, *klumusht* “*qumësht*”, *zglodhi* “*zgjodhi*”, *glëm* “*gjëmb*”, *gluha* “*gjuha*”, *i glatë* “*i gjatë*”, *ulk* “*ujk*”, *alk* “*ajk*, etc.”.

- Lack of *-y-* phoneme, which is replaced by *-i-* or *-u-* for example *di*, “*dy*”, *dizet* “*dyzet*”, *qipi* “*qypi*”, *gjiq* “*gjyq*”, *mbit* “*mbyt*”, *dufeq* “*dyfek*”, *burek* “*byrek*”, etc.

- Pairs of vowels like *ua*, *ie*, for example *grua*, *fiell* “*fyell*”, *ftua*, *u thie* “*u thye*”, *qiell*, *u mërie*, *prrua*, *thua*, etc., are still preserved.

- *-l-* consonant is still preserved, which in the rest of the literary Albanian language is replaced by *-j-* for example *gola* “*goja*”, *val* “*vaj*”, etc.

- The phoneme *-ë-* is silent when paired with consonants like *-p-* or *-m-*, being regularly pronounced, for example *kushuri*, *ulurij*, *klumusht*, etc.

- Silent *-ë-* is still preserved at the end of word like *bukë*, *lugë*, etc.

- Supporting *-ë-* is still preserved in words like *lidhë*, *pjekë*, *vatë*, *patë*, etc.

- The *-ë-* phoneme is still preserved before nasal consonant for example *m,n,nj* like, *mënd*, *zëmër*, *vënd*, *qëndër*, *bërna*, *dhën*, *thëmërr*, *ndënja*, *ëmër*, etc.

- It still preserves the 29 consonants.

- *-r-* phoneme is still found equally to the literary language, for example *pleqëri*, *rëra*, *mora*, *hira* “*hyra*”, *zura shpura*, *krua*, etc.

- Pairs of consonants like *mb*, *nd*, *ng*, *ngj*, are mostly reduced to either their first or the second letter, for example *bleth* “*mbledh*”, *bjell* “*mbjell*”, *baro* “*mbaro*”, *pesëmëdhjetë* “*pesëmbëdhjetë*”, *kumull* “*kumbull*”, *plum* “*plumb*”, *drishe* “*ndryshe*”, *bërna* “*brenda*”, *dreq* “*ndreq*”, *daj* “*ndaj*”, *gorth* “*ngordh*”, *grehu* “*ngrehu*”, *garkoj* “*ngarkoj*”, *gjir* “*ngjyrë*”, *zegjin* “*zengjin*”, *e një t'ju njethur bëra* “*e një t'ju ngjethur bëra*”, etc.

- The pair of consonants *-fsh-* is almost unreduced, for example *klofsh* “*qofsh*”, *fshat*, *kafshë*, *fshesë*, *fshi* and sometimes it is also found as part of the group *-psh-*, for example *kapshore* “*kafshatë*”

The consonant *-z-* has often turned into *-x-*, for example *xarr* “*zvarrë*”, *xerk* “*zverk*”, *xathur* “*zbathur*”, etc.

There are often other transformation like: *xhurape* “*çorape*”, *xhap* “*çap*”, *maç* “*mace*”, etc.

The spoken language of the town of Konispol is often distinguished for its long, very long, short and middle length vowel, such as *xhade: pllaje::*, *Qamile:,pë::*, *ve::*, *kërce::ll*, *kongji::ll*,

the::r – very long vowels *pre:r, kla:r, tërshë:r, kasa:r* – long vowels ; *buk, fik, mes, shes, vjeth* – short vowels ; *pra.lli, tru.ri, gj.ri, kalli.ri* – middle length vowels.

In terms of emphasis, emphases usually falls on the first syllable, for example *ái, kí, dhóksan, çákall, kúfall, lárosh, fólosh, etc.*

- Emphases in the words borrowed in the Turkish language usually falls on the last syllable, for example *trahaná, maharmá, xhadé, misír, babá, kasmá, Memé, Zeqiré, etc.*

MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE SPOKEN LANGUAGE OF THE TOWN OF KONISPOL

Similarly to its characteristic phonetics, we could divide its morphological features by structural and functional criteria.

NOUN

Gender. The current Konispol language still has three genders for nouns, i.e. masculine, feminine, and neutral. Even though the neutral gender is being unified in the standard language, there is still some use of such gender (especially in the accusative case). For example, *njesh brumët* “ngjesh brumin”, *sosa grurët* “mbarova grurin”, *isht një lloj plage që të ha misht* “është një lloj plage që të ha mishin”, etc.

Nouns of Turkish origin are usually of the feminine gender, for example *baba-babai, xhaxha-xhaxhai, etc.*

- Noun forms. The definite form of singular masculine nouns, which end by *-ua* in their definite form, take an *-o* vowel and *-i* as an ending, for example *ftua-ftoi, krua-kroi, thua-thoi, prrua-prroi, etc.*

- Number. Some nouns make their plural by *-nj*, for example *shkop-shkopinj, kongjill-kongjinj, ulli-ullinj, etc.*

Others by -ënj or -enj, for example prrenj, lumenj, etc.

Many nouns form their plural form by *-ër, -nj, -a, -ra, etc.* For example *çamër, gonër, nipër, qenër, thonj, pënj, thika, driza, bucela, hasmerira, tepsira, avllira, misirëra, krushqira, etc.*

Plural form by the use of metaphones, for example *cjap-cjepër, dollap-dollepër, shtrat-shtretër, etc.* is also quite popular.

- Cases. The ablative case is often formed by *-sh*, for example *manaferrash, llafesh, burrash, sherr grash, val ullinjsh, glas pulash, etc.*

In many cases (even though this is almost disappearing), the accusative case has not only its regular form, which corresponds with the standard form, but it is also formed by the ending –ë, for example *mori malë* “*mori malin*”, *shpuri djalë* “*shpuri djalin*”, etc.

ADJECTIVES

Adjectives are distinguished by one another by the respective particles for both genders, for example *i mir- e mirë*, *i lier- e lier* “*i liyer*”, *i billur- e billur* “*i mbyllur*”, etc. the adjective “*i bukur*” forms its masculine form through palatalization, for example *të buqur- të bukura* (*feminine*)

PRONOUN

- The personal pronoun for the first person, *unë*, is used in its dimple phonetic form, for example *u* for *u-unë*. Plural pronoun for the first and second person are dominated by the forms of *neve-juve*

Neve-ne

Juve-ju.

As for the indicative pronoun, the pronoun *ky, kjo*, which is the standard language, are found in Konispol as *ki, qo*. For example *ki djal isht i zgluar. Qo bila isht e zonja*.

- The spoken language of Konispol includes interrogative pronouns like *çil, çila, kush, ç’, çish, çili, çila, çilët, çilat*, as well as other forms they take during declination. For example *e kujtja isht qo bil* “*e kujt është kjo vajze*”, *çish u dive?* “*si u gdhive?*”

VERBS

Verbs are the part of grammar that demonstrates most of the distinguishing features compared to the standard Albanian.

Thus, verbs in the present tense, active voice, do not change their ending during declination, but they take ending *-t* in both singular and plural form, for example

Bërtit-bërtitnim-bërtitni-bërtitin, ulurit-uluritnim-uluritni-uluritnin, etc.

- Some verbs have preserved the following form in the third person, for example

Hanga- hangëm piva-pivëm

Hange-hangët pive-pivët

Hangu-hangën piu-pijtën

- The imperfect past tense of certain verbs is formed by homophones as used in the present and simple past tense

Zgledhje-zgjidhje
Hedhje-hidhje
Japje-jepje
Shpirje-shpije
Virje-vije

Verbs ending in consonants take *-ij* in the first person singular, second person singular, and lose the *-ej* and *-jim ending*, and *ijt, -ijn*, in the three persons of their plural form.

<i>Hedhij – hedhjim</i>	<i>gledhij – gledhjim</i>
<i>Hedhje – hedhjët</i>	<i>glidhje - glidhët</i>
<i>Hedh – hidhjën</i>	<i>glidh – glidhjën</i>

- The most popular verbs end in *-j; -je; -j* or *-ej* for the three persons of their singular form and *-jim; -jit; -jin*; for the three persons of their plural form,

For example

Shkluaaj – shkluaajim (shihnim)
Shkluaje – shkluajit
Shkluej – shkluajin

The imperfect past tense of the auxiliary verbs *jam (to be)* and *kam (to have)* are similar to the old forms of the Albanian language, for example

<i>Unë jeshi – keshi</i>	<i>ne jeshëm - keshëm</i>
<i>Ti jeshe – keshe</i>	<i>ju jeshët - keshët</i>
<i>Ai/ajo ish – kish</i>	<i>ata/ato ishjën – kishjën</i>

- The future tense in the spoken language of Konispol is formed by the verb *do* or by the auxiliary verb *kam*, plus practical *për* and verb noun, for example *do veç e do viç shpejt* “do vesh e do vish shpejt”, *kam për t’vatur shpejt* “kam për të vajtur shpejt”.

- The subjunctive form in this dialect corresponds with ending *-ç*, for example *të veç, të rroç, të mësoç, të jeç, të shkoç, të jetoç, të jeç golëmël atje ku të veç* “të jesh gojëmbël atje ku të vesh”. Sometimes between the root of the verb and its ending *-ç*, there is an *-ior* –efor example *të fshiç, të nisiç, të bieç, etc.*

As for the third person of the present tense in the subjunctive form, we notice two forms:

- a) –ë ending
- b) -ij ending, such as *të bjerij, të shpjerij, të lërij...*

PASSIVE VERBS

As for the indicative form in the second singular form, what is characteristic is that verbs end in – *ej*, for example *pse mërgonej kur të gjithë ktu të duan ti*. “pse mërgohej (largohej) kur të gjithë këtu të duan ty”.

• The composed forms of the past tense of the diathesis represent an interesting case. They are formed by the auxiliary verb *kam (to have) + past participle*, with an *-u* before the verb, similar to the simple past tense of this diathesis. For example

- U kish bënë* – it was done
- U kish thënë* – it was said
- U kishmësuar* – it was taught, etc.

ADVERBS

Adverbs appear in some old forms in the spoken language of Konispol, for example time adverbs *ahjere, akomi, akomina, kasdej, kasmot, kasnjënadës, etc. Do vi tanjani po bille* “do vi tani po mbylle”.

Quantity adverbs, for example *çik, pakogjë, njëpik, etc. një çik do rrijm* “pak do të rrimë”

Manner adverbs *paramera, aradha, aqerjo, avash-avash, kuturu, kasht e koqe*.

PREPOSITIONS

The most popular prepositions in the spoken language of Konispol are *jaram, në, nek, bi, ga, etc. Bjer ga ajo an/ bjeri nga ajo anë*.

CONJUGATIONS

There is a wide use of conjugations in the spoken language of Konispol, such as *edhe, e/hem. Hem i brrite, hem e deshe/ edhe i bërtite edhe e deshe. haj, a hot/në mos, etc.*

LEXICOLOGICAL AND PHRASEOLOGICAL WEALTH OF THE SPOKEN LANGUAGE OF KONISPOL

The bases of Konispol dialect is the *çam* language.

Given that the town of Konispol is generally mountains, which has led people into making their living through livestock, there are a lot of words from this background, for example *frenxat, kolive, mushtjerr, çokane, nangërr, dubek, folosh, vakrrosh, bagël, etc.*

As for agricultural terminology, we may mention words like *ris, thekër, misir, parmënd, xhuf, etc.*

Regarding fruit trees, there are word like *lëngël, kuqël, belic, bishtël (dardha); perdhikul (lloj fiku), çokall, bokall (fik i pabërë), argle (lloj ulliri), luturvi (vendit ku bëhet vaji), lostër (mbetjet e ullirit).*

Gardening includes words like *sfekël (type of cabbage), maqinidhjos, anth, dhjosëm, llapsana, shinap, korkale, resat, etc.* It is worth mentioning certain words used to name objects, phenomena, and different items, for example *posh-shami koke, mandible-shami dore, korth-kore buke, rrethi i sitës, etc., kopan (fëmija i vogël lidhur në pelena), buhar (oxhak), maharma (peshqir), cep (petë byreku, lëvozhga e frutave).*

Cooking represents an important part of the vocabulary; *trahana, klumushtuar, kostuar, rigonël, tërhollës, djathtuar, etc.*

- Adverbs are also important to mention, because they are either rarely used or not used at all in either dialects, including Tosk dialect.

For example *dej, dejbrëma, kasdej, kasnjënadës, etc.*

PHRASEOLOGICAL PHRASES

There is an interesting use of phrases like *të krrefsha gavat, të hangsha gërnjallin, vafsh e mos ardhç, etc.*

PUZZLES (children games)

Një katuaa plot me kual të kuq. Çish isht? (shega)

Një arap kërcen si lap. Çish isht? (pleshti)

Nam çik cinxërrinë se ta dërgoj prapë. Çish isht? (zigji-pesha)

Mos të kesh njapes a gjasht, vallahi do beteç jasht. Çish isht? (shkallat)

Arrnavale, karnavale, vjen me for e shkel kadale. Çish isht? (bora)

Në pill lehet, në pill rritet, me di kokale vritet. Çish isht? (morri)

Në pill lehet, në pill rritet, në fshat del e bën qesat. Çish isht? (dubeku i klumshtit)

Një arap i zi pjell e bën flori. Çish isht? (ulliri)

THE DEVELOPMENT OF KONISPOLY LANGUAGE AND ITS TRANSFORMATION TO WORDS STANDARD LANGUAGE

As mentioned above, the spoken language of Konispol belongs to the Tosk dialect and south Tosk subdialect. The people living in this town call themselves *Konispolat* and they prefer to be generalized as *çam*.

I managed to collect information in this article which shows that the spoken language of the town of Konispol is largely similar to that of Çamëria, but it still preserves its authenticity.

There is an obvious tendency today towards combining the old spoken language with the standard one. Thus, a lot of old forms are less used, such as the indicative pronoun *qo* (kjo), *çish* (what), *çila*, *çili* and many other forms.

It is worth mentioning that the inhabitants of town of Konispol have very well preserved their language. This is largely attributed to mothers, women and sisters, who have influenced their children, imposing this dialect on them in a firm manner. This is mainly because unlike Saranda, Konispol is a place where you don't usually hear Greek music, where people do not speak Greek, not to mention that there are no Greek names used for streets, bars, etc.

THE SOCIOLOGICAL ASPECT OF ETHNOGRAPHY OF THE SPOKEN LANGUAGE OF KONISPOL

I have chosen to look at some of the greetings, wishes, and curses used in the spoken language of Konispol.

Through their cradle songs, mothers express their human wish for their children to grow healthy and fast. They also wish that their children honor them, and they become worth it of "songs dedicated to them", similar to the famous men of all our times and our country.

We find such wishes expressed through phrases like: "*M'u bëfsh trim si Pirro Burri*", "*Marko Boçari*", "*Ali Pasha*", "*Naj naj kuni kuni/djalënë te zërë gjumi /naj naj fli mor bir/ fli se gjumi të bën mirë*"

The birth of a baby is a great joy. Given birth to baby boys was experienced with a lot of more emotion than baby girls, which would make women feel guilty. Thus, I managed to identify a song about a young mother, who gave birth to two girls, one after the other. Instead of wishing her daughter, her own mother send her the following message "*haj e piqi të dija*".

Some of the most popular wished are:

T'ju rrojë e t'ju bëhet plak me mjekërr "t'u rroj e të bënet plak me mjekrra"

Usually, babies are named by the elderly in their families. In these cases, the wishes include: “*Sa bëft aj nën dhe (gjyshi, gjyshja), aq bëft ki bi dhe*”

Weddings represent another important moment in one’s life. The same applies to the town of Konispol. Some of the most joyful wishes made in these cases are; “*nuse ktu ku kalle këmët, ktu t’i lëç dhëmët*”.

Death is another important moment in people’s life, which is certainly reflected in specific expressions used in Konispol: “*t’u ket len uratën*”, “*Të rroni ju e çish ju do zëmra*”, “*T’u rroj burri e fëmila*”, etc.

In addition to these deeply-felt and originally expressions, I’d like to particularly mention wishes made for celebrations, birthdays, etc. “*barësi e bar’ e mir’ ishalla*”, “*Kloft i bar’ e i gëzuar ki vit*”, “*u bëfç 100 vjeç*”, etc.

In addition to these wishes, which are still used today, the language, as any other language, includes also curses. Some of the curses used in Konispol include “*mos të dift’ dita*”, “*të kloftë harram klumushti i nanës*”, etc.

The use of metaphors does not seem to be very popular in the spoken language of Konispol. However, I did manage to find some indications of it. Probably it has been more used before ... “*Iku çau ferrat*” referring to someone who hides, who goes to some unknown place. “*vate për dhjam qeni*” referring to a person or a thing being wasted, “*mori atë që i takonej*” referring to someone getting what they deserve in their life.

DIALECT THROUGH THREE GENERATIONS

In order to address how dialect has changed over generations, I refer to three generations, the grandmother (88), her daughter (69), and her granddaughter (45).

Ne s’keshm njëher me se t’mirreshjëm. Ja, binim ato punrat bërna, fshinim kalivet, i binim për t’gën’ agajt e banim fëmilën. U kesh bën shum dantella kur jeshnja sa ti, tani s’sho dot më, po po të shohinj do binja akomi...Ooo ingëm ne vajtëm po bini ju se do ju qeshin bota. U kur u marrtova se kesh par hiç atë, drishe ne, jo si ju sot që i dini të gjitha. U bëra di vashaz e tre djelm. Të gjith imarrtovo e fëmilërova. Të marrtonja edhe atë atje e le të vdes pstatj

Kufeta Dishati 88 vjeç

U jesh pesëmëdhjetë vjeç kur më vdiq babai. Jesh e marrtuar e kesh edhe vajzën e madhe ahëre. Ai ish hem i sëmurë e hem plak se qe marrtuar shum më i madh ga nuja. Dënja tri dit te babaj, m’u në gone të tij e më dukej në sabah sikur e kesh përpara sive të gjall.

B.SH 69 vjeç

Shi të tëthom u tani. U ika se kta nuk dojën që u të mirrja atë. Po edhe ai banej një xhaket që qe allosoj për kohën. Po kta donin të më marrtonin me një ga Saranda. Eu... më mir ktu se sa me atë tjetrin. Tani vemi argat te greku të di e punojmë. Çish do bijm, duam të ham e të bajm edhe djalin në shkoll të lart. M. L 45 vjeç

CONCLUSIONS

The spoken language of Konispol is part of the southern Tosk subdialect, and is very similar to the çam spoken language.

The town of Konispol is located in the most southern part of Albania. It is built on 250-300 meters above the sea level, and surrounded by the mountain of Saraqindi in the north, Cjepuri on the east, Narta Hills in the south, and the Jon see in the west.

As for the phonetic features of this language, we notice the following characteristics:

- Lack of –y vowel and its replacement by –ior–u
- No diphthongs, just pairs of vowels like ua, ie.
- Presence of long, very long, average, and short phonemes.
- Older pairs of consonants like kl, and gl are still preserved.
- Consonant –l, which is replaced by –j across the Albanian language is also still preserved.
- The analytical forms of the past tense of passive verbs are formed by their active voice plus –u in the end.
- The suffix –l is used to form action verbs or motion nouns.
- –i vowel is preserved.
- Silent –ë phoneme accompanied by consonants p or m is pronounced as –u in such phonetic conditions.
- Silent –e is preserved in word ending.
- All the 29 consonants of the Albanian language are preserved.
- Pairs of consonants like mb, nd, ngj, and ng are often preserved.
- The fsh pair is still preserved, unchanged.
- Consonant z is often transformed to x.

Morphological characteristics are also worth mentioning.

Thus, we may classify the morphological distinctions by structural and functional criteria. Characteristics are thus found with nouns, adjectives, pronouns, verbs, adverbs, prepositions, and conjunctions.

The basis of the spoken language of Konispol is the çam dialect. Rare words enriching its lexicology are related mainly with livestock, agriculture, cooking, diseases, etc.

I wish and hope to have brought a part of the history, culture, ethnography, and lexicology of the spoken language of Konispol. I also hope to be able some day to deepen my research into what I consider to be my first step in knowing myself, and my roots.

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